

Changes in the Viscosity of Gelatine Sols in the process of Gelation.

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It has been observed that the melting and setting temperatures of gelatine gels and sols are not identical. The difference observed in the melting and setting temperatures of gelatine gels and sols becomes smaller with increasing time of observation. Moreover, melting point determinations of gels, as recorded by different workers, are not reproducible. Our researches show that the setting and melting temperatures are identical, if sufficient time be allowed for observation.

In the course of our observations on the hysteresis in the sol-gel transformation of gelatine gels of various concentrations the following results were obtained, for different intervals of time.

TABLE I.

	Conc. (%)	...	10			20			40			
Melting	{	Temp. ...	85°	30°	25°	40°	35°	30°	40°	35°	30°	
		Time (min.) ...	2	4	*	2	3	*	3	9	*	
Solidifying	{	Temp. ...	20°	25°	30°	20°	25°	30°	35°	25°	30°	35°
		Time (min.) ...	6	17	**	3	5	14	**	2	7	**

* Does not melt in 1 hr.

** Does not set in 1 hr.

By extrapolating our results, we find that the melting and setting points become identical for 10 per cent. gelatine sol in 85 minutes, for 20 per cent. gelatine sol in 25 minutes and for 40 per cent. gelatine sol in 20 minutes. That is, the greater the concentration of the gel, the less is the time at which the melting and setting temperatures become the same. Similar results were obtained with soap gels in various alcohols and water. It will also be found from the above table, that no firm gels of gelatine of any concentration can be obtained above 33°.

It is well known that the gelatine sols show remarkable change in viscosity on keeping. P. von Schroeder (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, **43**, 75) recognised that when a gelatine solution is kept at a high temperature, at which it does not gelatinise, the viscosity decreases continuously until it reaches a considerably low value. On the other hand, he showed that when a gelatine solution is kept at its setting temperature or below it, the viscosity regularly increases till it finally sets. Arisz (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1915, **7**, 1) has also shown with an Ostwald-viscometer for glycerol sols of gelatine that the viscosity of a gelatine sol, at its temperature of setting, is always less than the viscosity of the same gelatine sol when obtained from the gel condition. If, however, the gelatine sols be kept at the temperature of observation for a preferably long time, the viscosities approach the same value. Similarly it has been reported by Davies and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1526) that the viscosity of gelatine solutions increases with the age. We have noticed remarkable changes in viscosity of gelatine sols with ageing, at temperatures not far off from their melting and setting temperatures, and hence a measurement of viscosity near the melting or the setting temperatures is important. We have already reported that in all the sol-gel transformations, the phenomenon of hysteresis is remarkably diminished by sowing the sols, which are in the process of gelation, with the already formed gels of the same substance. We have, therefore, also investigated the effect of sowing of gels on the viscosity of gelatine sols.

In our investigations, we have used Kahlbaum's Goldrück sample and the following results were obtained on the moisture, ash content and p_H of the solution,

Moisture—10.28 per cent.; Ash—1.24 per cent.

p_H (colorimetric, Michaelis' method)—5.3.

Gelatine sols of various concentrations were prepared as far as possible under identical conditions. Each sol was divided into two parts, I and II. Part I was immediately brought to the temperature of the thermostat, maintained at $45^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ and then the temperature of the thermostat was lowered by 5° up to 25° for the observation of the viscosities at the lower temperatures. Part II was first allowed to set and kept in the thermostat at 25° and then the temperature was gradually increased by 5° up to 45° for the observation of viscosities at the higher temperatures.

TABLE II.
Gelatine sol (2%).

Temp.	Time (min.)	45°	40°	35°	30°	25°	
Abs. viscosity (Parts I & II).	6	I	0-01088	0-01126	0-01237	0-01332	0-01752
		II	0-01065	0-01127	0-01244	0-01402	0-01790
	11	I	0-01088	0-01129	0-01233	0-01339	0-01762
		II	0-01062	0-01115	0-01226	0-01384	0-01781
	16	I	0-01088	0-01129	0-01239	0-01339	0-01789
		II	0-01062	0-01112	0-01213	0-01376	0-01781

The viscosities were measured by Ostwald's viscometer. The changes in the viscosity with time and temperature in the two cases are given below.

TABLE III.
Gelatine sol (3 %).

Temp.	Time (min.)	Absolute viscosity.	
		Part I	Part II
45°	6-5	0-01403	0-01439
	11-5	0-01407	0-01439
	16-5	0-01415	0-01430
40°	6-5	0-01638	0-01632
	11-5	0-01653	0-01616
	16-5	0-01665	0-01616
35°	7	0-01883	0-01963
	12	0-01884	0-01868
30°	7	0-01895	0-01851
	8	0-02191	0-02647
	15	0-02227	0-02554
	21	0-02254	0-02509
25°	15	0-03213	0-04444
	22	0-04291	0-03026

TABLE IV.
Gelatine sol (10%).

Temp.	Time (min.)	Absolute viscosity.	
		Part I	Part II
50°	12	0.06553	0.06170
	32	0.06770	0.08060
45°	12	0.07426	0.06760
	33	0.07685	0.06633
40°	25	0.9303	0.07326
35°	—	Extremely viscous.	Extremely viscous.
30°	—	"	"
25°	—	Sets to a jelly.	Jelly.

It is observed that there is a considerable difference in the viscosities of the gelatine sols prepared at a higher and a lower temperature (also *cf.* Davies and co-workers, *loc. cit.*), the sol prepared at a lower temperature showing greater viscosity than the sol prepared at a higher temperature. Our results show that in general the viscosity increases with time when a gelatine sol prepared at a higher temperature is kept in a bath of a lower temperature, whilst the sol obtained from a gel shows a decrease in the viscosity with time, at a temperature higher than the melting point of the gel.

It will be apparent from our results that in the case of 2% gelatine sols, the ageing effect on the viscosity (a decrease or increase) is appreciable even within a short interval of time from a temperature of about 35°; in the case of 3% sol, this change appears from 40° and in the case of 10% sol, this is observable even at 50°. It is therefore evident that the change in the viscosities of gelatine solutions with time may be either towards an increase or decrease, according to the condition of the solution under investigation. The changes with time are also maximum at the temperature nearing gelation or melting points in the sol-gel transformation and the effect of time continuously diminishes, as the temperature is increased and is far beyond the melting or setting temperature.

Davies and Oakes (*loc. cit.*) observed that the viscosity of a sample of 1% gelatine solution, when kept in a bath of 35° immediately after its preparation, showed a tendency of increase. The

sample, previously set to a firm gel and kept at 30°, also showed a similar change. As the viscosity measurements were carried out by them, in viscometer tubes, it is apparent that the gel must have melted to a less viscous mobile liquid, which again showed an increase in viscosity. This latter result appears to us rather peculiar and accordingly, we have carried out a similar set of experiments with gelatine sols.

In the following cases, the viscosities were determined under two conditions, namely, the sol was (i) brought down from 50° to the lower temperature at which the viscosities were determined and (ii) allowed first to set, then kept in the ice chest for one hour and again brought to the temperature of observation.

The setting temperatures of a 3% sol of p_H 7.6 and a 10% sol of p_H 7.7 were 15° and 23° respectively.

TABLE V.

Gelatine sol (3%); $p_H = 7.6$.

Case 1.				Case 2.					
Temp. = 35°				Temp. = 35°					
Time (min.)	10	85	123	145	Time (min.)	60	120	200	275
Viscosity	0.02276	0.02304	0.02332	0.02345	Viscosity	0.02376	0.02334	0.02325	0.02313
Temp. = 45°				Temp. = 45°					
Time (min.)	15	48	85	125	Time (min.)	60	120	180	240
Viscosity	0.0174	0.01756	0.01763	0.01776	Viscosity	0.01568	0.01568	0.01550	0.01545

TABLE VI.

Gelatine sol (10%); $p_H = 7.7$.

Case 1.				Case 2.					
Temp. = 35°				Temp. = 35°					
Time (min.)	15	68	130		Time (min.)	75	140	200	250
Viscosity	0.1043	0.1077	0.1127		Viscosity	0.1048	0.1093	0.1020	0.1017
Temp. = 45°				Temp. = 45°					
Time (min.)	20	68	127	190	Time (min.)	60	130	200	250
Viscosity	0.08813	0.08854	0.08880	0.08896	Viscosity	0.08842	0.08450	0.07768	0.07142

It thus appears that 3 per cent. and 10 per cent. gelatine sols show an increase in viscosity with ageing, when brought down to 45°

or 35° from a higher temperature. On the other hand, the viscosity decreases when the sols are kept at 35° or 45° after they have formed gels, and hence our results are not in agreement with those of Davies and co-workers.

In a series of publications (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 184, 195; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 17) from these laboratories, we have shown that the sols of silicic, vanadic, tungstic, molybdic and antimonie acids contain sufficient quantities of these substances in the molecular condition, simple and aggregated, together with the colloidal particles. The simple molecules have a general tendency to aggregate and gradually merge into particles of colloidal dimension with age. Raising the temperature of the sol, when freshly prepared, causes the disintegration of the colloidal particles and aggregated molecules into simpler ones. Similar transition of the particles of the bigger size to the smaller size has been followed with gelatine sol during the process of heating. Arisz (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1915, 7, 22) showed that the Tyndall cone is very faint in gelatine sols at 70°, it gradually becomes stronger on cooling and weaker on rewarming. He found that the variations in the viscosity of gelatine sols were parallel with the changes in the strength of the Tyndall cone. Bachmann (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1911, 73, 125; 1912, 79, 202) has also found similar behaviour from ultramicroscopic observations during the gelation of silicic acid, gelatine and agar. It is therefore to be concluded that gelatine solutions at higher temperatures contain extremely fine particles of molecular dimensions which gradually polymerise to bigger aggregates and colloidal particles on cooling the sols.

We are of the opinion that in the gelatine solution, the following equilibrium exists:—

Smith (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 135) from his observations on the mutarotation of gelatine at various temperatures concludes: "At any intermediate temperature between 35° and 15°, there is a condition of equilibrium which may be represented by the equation

He believes that an increase in the form B parallels an increase in the viscosity.

Smith (*loc. cit.*) believes that a transition of the sol form A to gel form B is due to a polymerisation of gelatine molecules. Moore and Roaf (*Biochem. J.*, 1907, 2, 52) have shown from osmotic pressure measurements, that there is an aggregation of molecules, responsible for the change of osmotic pressure with time. Bogue (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1913) has shown that the rate of flow of gelatine sols in viscosity tube, plotted against the shearing stress, gives a straight line, which passes through the origin at higher temperatures. If, however, the temperature of gelatine sol be gradually lowered, the increase in the viscosity is rapid with the fall of the temperature, near the gelation point, and with the varying shearing stress, the rate of fall is hardly linear, especially with the lower values of the stress. It is found that the curves, when extrapolated, do not pass through the origin. From these results, it is apparent that the gelatine sol shows a plastic flow near the gelation temperature, indicating the formation of large number of colloidal particles at the expense of aggregated and simple molecules, present in the sol.

We are of opinion that in gelations, as observed in the reversible sol-gel transformations, an aggregation of simple molecules is an inevitable consequence. Thus in the case of gelatine sols, gelation occurs when a sufficient quantity of aggregated molecules and colloidal particles are present. As the number of aggregated molecules and necessarily the colloidal particles is smaller in a dilute solution than in a concentrated one, it is evident that a greater lowering of temperature is necessary for the formation of the gel from a dilute solution than from a concentrated one. As however the amount of aggregated molecules rapidly diminishes with increasing temperature, it follows that gelation cannot take place above a certain temperature, with any concentration of gelatine sols. Thus with gelatine sols of various concentrations, no gel is obtained even with 40 per cent. solution above 33°. Our viscosity measurements on 10 per cent. gelatine sol show a distinct change with time even at a temperature of 50° and we are of opinion that an increase in viscosity with time is associated with the formation of more and more of aggregated molecules and *vice versa*.

It may be of interest to add here that Andrade in a recent communication (*Nature*, 1930, 125, 583) also remarks: "True association, in which the molecules are bound together in clusters of two or more for a time large compared to the intervals between collisions, leads, with the mechanism postulated, to an increase of viscosity." A

sudden increase, in the viscosity of gelatine sols with the fall in temperature near the setting temperature is most probably due to the formation of a large number of aggregated molecules and colloidal gelatine, near the gelation temperature.

It may be stated here that sol form A and gel form B of Smith correspond to simple and aggregated molecules. Above 35°, the number of simple molecules preponderates and at 16°, there is an abundance of aggregated molecules and colloidal gelatine. Between 16° and 35°, the transformation of simple molecules to aggregated molecules and colloidal gelatine is very rapid, with the lowering of temperature. Davies and Oakes (*loc. cit.*) have concluded from the ageing effect on the viscosity of gelatine sols that the existence of the gel form B is only possible below 38°, as the viscosity of gelatine sols continuously increases with age below this temperature and above this, the viscosity decreases with age. Our experimental results with the gelatine sols of a high concentration (10%) however distinctly show an increase in the viscosity with age, when prepared at a higher temperature and then kept for observation even at 50°. On the other hand, with dilute gelatine sols (2 and 3%), changes in viscosity with ageing were only significant between temperatures 35° and 40° and below.

In the previous publication (*loc. cit.*) from this laboratory, we have shown that sowing the reversible sols with already formed gels more readily affects the gelation of sols. The results recorded in the following table show a remarkable increase in the viscosity of the sol, when it is sowed with already formed gel of the same concentration as the sol.

Table VII.

Viscosity changes with Sowing.

		gelatine sol (2%).					
<i>Without sowing.</i>					<i>With sowing.</i>		
Temp.	Time (min.)	30°	35°	Temp.	Time (min.)		
Viscosity {	12	0.01850	0.01448	Viscosity {	13	0.02305	0.02186
	22	0.01875	0.01448		23	0.02319	0.02186
	32	0.01906	0.01448		33	0.02333	0.02186

It is interesting to find that there is a greater percentage of increase in the viscosity of the sol, kept at a higher temperature (35°) than at a lower temperature (30°). An increase in the viscosity of sols of gelatine in the presence of already formed, gels show that more of aggregated molecules and colloidal gelatine are formed when the gels are added to the sols. As the sols at 30° contain greater number of aggregated molecules and colloidal gelatine than at 35°, it is apparent that the effect of sowing is more marked at 35° than at 30°. It must be understood that at temperatures above 35°, this effect of sowing, namely to cause an increase in viscosity, will decrease, because the gel melts quickly at temperatures above 35° and thus the aggregating influence on the molecules present in the gelatine sols becomes less effective.

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